

University Graduates Employability skills and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated University Graduates Employability skills and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State. The study was carried out in Rivers State. Two specific objectives, two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study consists of One Thousand Two Hundred and ninety-four (1294), Educational management graduates in Rivers State University. The sample size consists of 306 Educational management graduates (Social studies and economic option) in Rivers State using Taro Yamane formula. The instrument that was used for this study was a self-structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts, two experts in the field of study and one in measurement and evaluation. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument that was used for the study, test re-test method was adopted, scores obtained were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84 meaning the instrument is appropriate and reliable for the study. Data collected from the respondents was analyze using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient to answer the research question and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that university curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them. Entrepreneurship education in the universities should be adequately funded. This can be achieved through increase in the budgetary allocation to the universities by the government.

Keyword: Uuniversity, Graduates, Employability, skills, Communication, Problem Solving Labour Market and Demand.

INTRODUCTION

Everything in this world today has changed tremendously including technological development, economic development and most of the works needs to operate globally in order to survive the competition which exists in the world these days. This change has created an impact on the nature of work where a high level use of technology is a necessity to compete in the global arena. Ogundele and Lawal (2018) opined that there is no doubt the emergence of technology has brought changes in the ways people are doing things. Hence, a more flexible workforce with advanced technical skills coupled with well-developed generic skills such as creative thinking, problem solving and analytical skills, is greatly needed by the employer in industry in order to meet the challenges faced by business. Faced with stiff global competition, an arising concern is that current graduates do not match the needs of business.

According to Khir (2016), graduates now are lacking in both technical know-how and generic skills.

Competence refers to the fusion of both domains of specific knowledge and generic skills, so the efforts to increase graduates' competence must cover both areas. This has been highlighted in the Ninth Malaysia Plan (Jailani, 2016). Educational institutions have come under intense pressure to equip students with more than just the academic skills. A number of reports issued by employers have urged universities to make more explicit efforts to develop the 'key', 'core', 'transferable', 'soft', 'employable' and/or 'generic skills' needed in many types of employment.

Labor market as one of the driving forces of the content and quality of education attributes high value to international recognition of qualifications and education. Since labour market uses and applies the learning outcomes in real life, quality of education and training policy cannot exist separately from it. The pressure of global competition means that graduates need to offer an employer more than academic skills traditionally represented by the subject and degree class. Since the

1990s, there were numerous reports from government, industry, higher education agencies and researchers urged the higher education sector to bring employability skills into the students' learning experience (Mason, Williams & Cranmer, 2016). The demand for labor is an economics principle derived from the demand for a firm's output. That is, if demand for a firm's output increases, the firm will demand more labor, thus hiring more staff. Labour market is given by Derek Bosworth, Peter Dawkins and Thorsten Stromback (2016) who state that the labour market is the place where supply and demand meet, working to determine the price and quantity of the work performed. Michel Didier (2017) defines the market as a means of communication through which sellers and buyers will inform each other about what they have, what they need and the prices that they ask or propose, before closing the transaction.

The labour market is the market in which the amount of services that correspond to tasks well established in the job description, are offered for a price or remuneration (Boeri, Van Ours, 2013), that is, to exist on the labour market it is necessary for the work be rewarded. The labour market is and has to be regulated. In the dictionary of labour law (2017), Beligrădeanu and Stefanescu (2017) define the labour market as "the confrontation between the supply and demand of labour in a given time frame and a geographic area that is usually completed through employment (with an individual employment contract). The worker (employee) means the person exerts his/hers activity based on an employment contract in a public or private company or institution, receiving in exchange a payment. On the labour market, companies act like buyers on the one hand, but also as bidders with regard to payment, working conditions, and individuals act as sellers, rendering available to employers their knowledge, skills and experience gained. The labour market operates on the principle of competition, the workers competing against each other in view of obtaining or retaining a position. On the other hand, employers compete to attract and maintain within the organizations, the employees that are efficient in the development of the activity and as a result make profit. Nita Dobrotă (2017) consider that the labour market is the economic space in which equity holders trade freely, as buyers (the demand), and the owners of the human resource (the supply), as sellers, in which the price mechanism of the work, the real wage, the free competition between economic operators and other specific mechanisms, adjust the labour supply and

demand. First and foremost, employees are not an abstract production factor, but human beings with families, desires and needs and only then, labour force (Samuelson, Nordhaus, 2011).

The labour market is one of the main components of the market economy along with the goods and capital market. From an economic perspective the labour market is one of the components of the production forces (Zamfir & Vlăsceanu, 2013). The workforce was and is the "living" factor that gives meaning to the economic life and is the main component of production factors, by whose direct or indirect intervention, all economic activities become possible. In statistical terms, the workforce is represented by the employed population (those working and those actively seeking work) to which the unemployed are added (Schiller, 2013).

Skill is the ability to perform a task to a predefined level of competence. Skills are often divided into two types: transferable or generic skills which can be used across large numbers of different occupations, and vocational skills which are specific occupational or technical skills needed to work within an occupation or occupational group (Proctor & Dutta, 2015). Skills mismatch is generally understood as various types of gaps or imbalances referring to skills, knowledge or competencies that may be of a quantitative or qualitative nature (Proctor & Dutta, 2015). It is the difference between the competence of the graduate and employers' expected competence needs. The various skills (generic skills) that employers now demand for in addition to academic skills are analytical, critical thinking, communication, entrepreneurial, decision making, IT (information technology), interpersonal, problem-solving, self-directed and numeracy skills. In Coleman (2009) skills are broken down into three categories. There are Job skills which are the skills needed for a specific job. For example a mechanic needs to know how to fix faulty brakes and an accountant should be able to draw up a balance sheet. They are enthusiasm, honesty and getting along well with people. Employers usually look for certain qualities and skills before hiring any staff member. These qualities and skills include punctuality, efficiency, and willingness to follow supervisor instructions, ability to get along with fellow workers, hard work and honesty.

Employability skills become a very important issue at the national, regional, and international labour market.

Employability skills are considered one missing link between education and training and the world of work. In the words of Sherer and Eadie, (2017), employability skills such as oral and written communication, the ability to work in team and interpersonal skills, that are foundational to both academic and workplace success. According to Dearing, (2017), the capacity of a fresh graduate to get work suitable to his educational qualification called employability skill. Besides, Buck and Barrick, (2017) stated that employability skills are attributes of employees, other than technical competence, that make the man asset to an employer. Similarly, Yorke and Knight, (2014) defined employability skills as a set of attainment that encompasses abilities, skills, knowledge, and personal qualifications which can make a person unique and qualified to perform achieving organizational goals and objectives. A good supply of skilled employable graduates in job is essential for national, economic and social well-being and the failure to equip young people with employability skills has far-reaching consequences. Moreover, Dearing, (2017) insisted that the present business graduates should possess oral communication, language proficiency, quantitative analysis, problem solving, creative and innovative thinking, learning skills, decision making, dependability, optimistic approach to responsibility, team player, punctuality, self-confidence, self-efficacy, adaptability or flexibility, etc.

Employability skills become a very important issue at the national, regional, and international labour market. Employability skills are considered one missing link between education and training and the world of work. Employability skills are sometimes referred to as professional, core, generic, key, and non-technical skills and are inherent to enhancing graduate work-readiness (Yorke & Knight, 2014). Employability skills typically considered important in developed economies are team working, communication, self-management, and analysis and critical thinking (Jackson, 2019). Robles (2012) describes soft skills as character traits that enhance a person's interactions, job performance, and career prospects the greatest feature of soft skills is that they are intangible and are not discipline specific, that is the application of these skills is not limited to one's profession. Soft skills are continually developed through practical application during one's approach toward everyday life and the workplace, teachable graduates develop their soft skills quicker. Soft skills are not easily

measurable like hard skills they are more of who we are than what we know and hard skills are those achievements that are included on a résumé, such as education, work experience, knowledge, and level of expertise. The researcher further explains that any form of education that does not equip its beneficiaries with skills to be self-reliant is a faulty system of education. It is against this background that the study will designed to ascertain the University Graduates Employability skills and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The universities in the recent times have witnessed unprecedented increase in the enrolment and turnout rates. Employability skills became an issue for the providers of undergraduates themselves. The prime intent of most students attending university is not to study or have in-depth knowledge of a course but to enhance their employability status (Stewart and Knowles, 2010). The problem of graduates' employability has been lingering on the lips of higher education administrators in different developing countries. These worries have been accorded the utmost priority in the current climate of the wider labour market. Policymakers continue to emphasize the importance of 'employability skills' in order for graduates to be fully equipped in meeting the challenges of an increasingly flexible labour market as these skills are rarely taught in school.

In spite of extensive ideas in employability skills being manufactured in tertiary institutions, the performance of graduates in the working environment is not in line with employer's expectations (Chavan & Carter, 2018). This is evident in Nigeria as expectations from graduates are not being fully met by the employers, most especially in the areas of self-development skills, job searching skills, leadership skills, conflict resolution, job interview skills, meta-cognitive skills, critical thinking skills and decision making. It is against this background that this study assessed University Graduates Employability skills and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State: implication for educational management.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine how University Graduates Employability skills and labour Market Demand in Rivers State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Find out how communication skills acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

- Determine how problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide the study.

- How communication skills acquired by university graduates do relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State?
- How problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates do relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State?

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population of the study consists of One Thousand Two Hundred and ninety-four (1294), Educational management graduates in Rivers State University. The sample size consists of 306 Educational management graduates (Social studies and economic option) in Rivers State using Taro Yamane formula. The

Table 1: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Communication Skills Acquired by University Graduates Relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Variable	N	R	R ¹	$\sqrt{V1 - R2}$	Percentage
communication skills acquired by university graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State	300	.865	.746	.502	75

The result of the analysis on table 1 revealed that the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient value of .865, .746 and .502 which indicate a high positive relationship between positive of communication skills acquired by university graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State. This findings implies that more communication skills acquired by university graduates will improve Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Research Question Two: How do problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State?

instrument that was used for this study was a self-structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire was tagged “University Graduates Employability Skills (UGESQ) and Labour Market Demand Questionnaire (LMDQ)” The questionnaire was divided into two sections, section A and section B. Section A elicit information of the bio data of the respondents while section B was structured in a modified four points Likert scale rating of Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4 points; Agreed (A) = 3 points, Disagree (DA) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. The instrument was validated by three experts, two experts in the field of study and one in measurement and evaluation. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument that was used for the study, test re-test method was adopted, scores obtained were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84 meaning the instrument is appropriate and reliable for the study. Data collected from the respondents was analyse using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient to answer the research question and to test the null hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: How do communication skills acquired by university graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State?

Table 2: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) between Problem Solving Skills Acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Variable	N	R	R ²	$\sqrt{V1-R^2}$	Percentage
problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State	300	-.848	.719	.530	92

The result of the analysis on table 2 revealed that the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient value of -.848, .719 and .530 which indicate a negative relationship between negative of communication skills acquired by university graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State. Hence, there is a negative relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates relates to Labour Market Demand in Rivers State. This findings implies that more problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates will improve Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State?.

Table 3: Showing t-test Statistical Analysis on the Relationship Between Communication Skills Acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Variable	N	R	Df	t-cal	t-crit	decision
communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State	300	.865	298	5.12	1.96	Rejected

It was observed that in table 3 that the correlation coefficient .865, t-calculated value 5.12 was greater than the table critical value 1.96 with df 298 at 5% probability level. To this end, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. The reason is that the t-calculated value 5.12 was greater than the table critical value 1.96.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

Table 4: Showing t-test Statistical Analysis on the Relationship Between Problem Solving Skills Acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Variable	N	R	Df	t-cal	t-crit	decision
problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State	300	-.848	298	4.21	1.96	Rejected

In table 4, the results obtained show that the correlation coefficient -.845, t-calculated value 4.21 was greater than the t-critical value 1.96 with df 298 at 5% probability level. Hence, the null hypothesis rejected. This is because the t-critical value 1.96 was less than the t-calculated value 4.21.

Summary of Major Findings

The following summary was achieved from the responses of the respondents.

From the findings, it was revealed that:

1. Research question 1 indicates that the respondents opined that there is a high and positive relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.
2. Research question 2 shows that the respondents opined that there is a high negative relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State
4. There is no significant relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of finding is done as thus;

Relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

The research questions answered and hypotheses tested at 5% probability level constitute the basis of discussion in this study. From table 1, the results revealed that the correlation coefficient .865, coefficient of determination .746, coefficient of alienation .502 while the percent of variation between lecturers' innovative assessment for learning and quality education was 75%. This showed that there is a positive relationship between communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

Testing the null hypothesis with t-test statistics, the results showed that t-calculated value 5.12 was greater than the table critical value 1.96 with df 298 at 5% probability level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This is because the table critical value 1.96 was less than the t-calculated value 5.12 indicating that communication skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State.

This finding is in agreement with the view of Abdulkarim (2012), who opined that Communication is the activity of conveying information through the exchange of thoughts, messages, or information, as by speech, visuals, signals, writing, or behavior. It is the meaningful exchange of information between two or more living creatures. The need for good communication skills, behaving appropriately in business situations and addressing situations in a professional manner are skills that businesses are looking for. In line with the view of Chen and Starosta, (2016) who opined that communication is a competence that can be regarded as the ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others. Communication, which is a vital skill for all professions, is at the core of the teaching profession in terms of teacher-student relationships. The teaching profession requires perfect communication skills, because the potential of lecturers to develop students is something related to effective communication. Thus, lecturers should both communicate effectively with others and carry out technical tasks to be successful professionals.

In agreement with the above view Naresh, (2017) opined that communication is indispensable to any organization's achievement. Communication is a critical point for human resource leaders which must be in alignment with the organization's management and its labour. Also, entrepreneur requires for effective communication skills to include how communication process helps the entrepreneur effect the managerial functions of planning, organizing, staffing, influencing, interacting, controlling, and co-ordinating.

In line with view of McShane and Von Glinow (2015) opined that Communication in business conveys to the vital management functions which include planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling. The management process of decision making, coordinating, delegation, centralization and decentralization are all surrounded by communication. Furthermore, the authors described communication as the process by which information is transmitted and understood between two or more people. Communication skills are also key factors in managing classrooms. Besides, communication competence is among the basic competencies of lecturers, because it is regarded as one of the skills required to improve student learning and achieving academic goals in classroom settings. As also remarked by Hurt, Scott, and McCroskey (2018), there is ‘‘a difference between knowing and teaching, and that difference is communication in the classroom’’. Communication styles of lecturers help students integrate their self-regulation with their inner motivation in autonomous classroom activities. The researcher also stated that Communication skills are also important in teaching. This awareness would help lecturers solve problems in the classroom.

Relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State

In research question two, in table 7, the results showed high negative correlation coefficient -0.848 coefficient of determination .719, coefficient of alienation .530 and the percentage influence of problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State was 72. The result revealed that there is a high negative relationship between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand

in Rivers State. Subjecting the data to t-test statistical on table 7, the results revealed that the correlation coefficient - .848 and t-calculated value 4.21 was greater than the t-critical value 1.96 with df 298 at 5% probability level. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that a high negative relationship exist between problem solving skills acquired by University Graduates and Labour Market Demand in Rivers State. It is an indication that problem solving skills affect University Graduates and Labour Market Demand.

The findings of this study is in agreement with that of Reeve (2010 who maintained that Problem-solving is a crucial skill that affects all life actions, from simple to complex. Problem-solving skills support individuals' ability to cope with behaviour. In agreement with the view of Jonassen, 2000; Funke, (2010) opined that problem-solving, which is regarded as a challenging process, requires behavioural, affective and cognitive actions to overcome the barriers on the way to the goal. Problem-solving is a multifaceted process with behavioural, affective and cognitive dimensions, and which is essential in handling critical situations and coping with problems. Hence, lecturers' problem-solving skills should be developed, because lecturers have to provide the best solution for issues that occur in every condition that they face in educational settings. It can also be asserted that teaching problem-solving to preserve lecturers could improve their skills on managing undesirable behaviours in the process of classroom setting. The researchers stated that Problem-solving give students and lecturers an opportunity to build an appropriate behaviour in classroom settings with the help of effective communication. Effective problem-solving skills of lecturers help them to communicate and interact with students and understand their roles in classroom.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis in the study, findings and discussion made. The researchers concluded that Communication Skills helps students Perform data analysis with a computer package and Ability to retrieve saved document. It was concluded that Problem-Solving Skills gives opportunity to utilize ones potentials. Courage to take extreme measures to identified problem and Ability to implement a plan of action to resolve problem.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The University curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them.
2. Entrepreneurship education in the universities should be adequately funded. This can be achieved through increase in the budgetary allocation to the universities by the government. With adequate funding, universities will be able to establish entrepreneurial development centers for practical work and the provision of training/instructional material for the programme.

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